

This is the EnvironmentlessEnvironment undimension model, which goes as followed:

- When no reality environment, then no reality either fixed or flexible.
- When no reality environment, then no reality base substance that is vapour.
- When no reality normal environment, then no reality reality anything apart from normal.
- And when the environment is no reality left, then the environment is no reality right, and when the environment is no reality right, then the environment is no reality left. And when the environment is no reality up, then the environment is no reality down, and when the environment is no reality down, then the environment is no reality up. And when the environment is no reality backwards, then the environment is no reality forwards, and when the environment is no reality forwards, then the environment is no reality backwards. And when the environment has no reality angles, then the environment has no reality counter-angles, and when the environment has no reality counter-angles, then the environment has no reality angles. And when the environment has no reality position, then the environment has no reality moment, and when the environment has no reality moment, then the environment has no reality position. And when the environment has no reality rotation, then the environment has no reality counter-rotation, and when the environment has no reality counter-rotation, then the environment has no reality rotation. And when the environment has no reality length, then the environment has no reality distance, and when the environment has no reality distance, then the environment has no reality length. And when the environment has no reality area, then the environment has no reality counter-area, and when the environment has no reality counter-area, then the environment has no reality area. And when the environment has no reality volume, then the environment has no reality counter-volume, and when the environment has no reality counter-volume, then the environment has no reality volume. And when the environment has no reality walls, then the environment has no reality counter-walls, and when the environment has no reality counter-walls, then the environment has no reality walls. And when the environment has a no reality floor, then the environment has no reality counter-floor, and when the environment has no reality counter-floor, then the environment has no reality floor. And when the environment has no reality ceiling, then the environment has no reality counter-ceiling, and when the environment has no reality counter-ceiling, then the environment has no reality ceiling. And when the environment has a no reality door, then the environment has a no reality counter-door, and when the environment has a no reality counter-door, then the environment has a no reality door. And when the environment is no reality indivisibly small, then the environment is no reality indivisibly large, and when the environment is no reality indivisibly large, then the environment is no reality indivisibly small. And when the environment is a no reality hallucination, then the environment is no reality psychedelic, and when the environment is no reality psychedelic, then the environment is a no reality hallucination. And when the environment is no reality quantum, then the environment is no reality counter-quantum, and when the environment is no reality counter-quantum, then the environment is no reality quantum. And when the environment is no reality nano, then the environment is no reality counter-nano, and when the environment is no reality counter-nano, then the environment is no reality nano. And when the environment is no reality micro, then the environment is no reality counter-micro, and when the environment is no reality counter-micro, then the environment is no reality micro. And when the environment is no reality macro, then the environment is no reality counter-macro, and when the environment is

no reality counter-macro, then the environment is no reality macro. And when the environment is no reality magical, then the environment is no reality counter-magical, and when the environment is no reality counter-magical, then the environment is no reality magical. And when the environment is no reality normal, then the environment is no reality counter-normal, and when the environment is no reality counter-normal, then the environment is no reality normal. And when the environment is no reality visioned, then the environment is no reality counter-visioned, and when the environment is no reality counter-visioned, then the environment is no reality visioned. And when the environment is no reality vapour, then the environment is no reality counter-vapour, and when the environment is no reality counter-vapour, then the environment is no reality vapour. And when the environment is no reality fixed, then the environment is no reality flexible, and when the environment is no reality flexible, then the environment is no reality fixed. And when the environment is no reality literal, then the environment is no reality pictured, and when the environment is no reality pictured, then the environment is no reality literal. And when the environment is no reality literal, then the environment is no reality counter-literal, and when the environment is no reality counter-literal, then the environment is no reality literal. And when the environment is no reality pictured, then the environment is no reality counter-pictured, and when the environment is no reality counter-pictured, then the environment is no reality pictured. And when the environment is no reality hallucinationed, then the environment is no reality counter-hallucinationed, and when the environment is no reality counter-hallucinationed, then the environment is no reality hallucinationed. And when the environment is no reality psychedelic, then the environment is no reality counter-psychedelic, and when the environment is no reality counter-psychedelic, then the environment is no reality psychedelic. And when the environment is no reality expectationed, then the environment is no reality counter-expectationed, and when the environment is no reality counter-expectationed, then the environment is no reality expectationed. And when the environment has no reality foreground, then the environment has no reality counter-foreground, and when the environment has no reality counter-foreground, then the environment has no reality foreground. And when the environment has no reality middleground, then the environment has no reality counter-middleground, and when the environment has no reality counter-middleground, then the environment has no reality middleground. And when the environment has no reality background, then the environment has no reality counter-background, and when the environment has no reality counter-background, then the environment has no reality background. And when the environment has an no reality alternative, then the environment has a no reality counter-alternative, and when the environment has a no reality counter-alternative, then the environment has a no reality alternative. And when the environment is no reality altered, then the environment is no reality counter-altered, and when the environment is no reality counter-altered, then the environment is no reality altered. When the environment has a no reality model, then the environment has a no reality counter-model, and when the environment has a no reality counter-model, then the environment has a no reality model. And when the environment has no reality facts, then the environment has no reality fiction, and when the environment has no reality fiction, then the environment has no reality facts. And when the environment has no reality facts, then the environment has no reality counter-facts, and when the environment has no reality counter-facts, then the environment has no reality facts. And when the environment has no reality fiction, then the environment has no reality counter-fiction,

and when the environment has no reality counter-fiction, then the environment has no reality fiction. And when the environment has no reality truth, then the environment has no reality counter-truth, and when the environment has no reality counter-truth, then the environment has no reality truth. And when the environment has no reality mirrors, then the environment has no reality counter-mirrors, and when the environment has no reality counter-mirrors, then the environment has no reality mirrors. And when the environment has no reality portals, then the environment has no reality counter-portals, and when the environment has no reality counter-portals, then the environment has no reality portals. And when the environment is no reality queensland, then the environment is no reality counter-queensland, and when the environment is no reality counter-queensland, then the environment is no reality queensland. And when the environment is no reality nuclear, then the environment is no reality counter-nuclear, and when the environment is no reality counter-nuclear, then the environment is no reality nuclear. And when the environment is no reality elemental, then the environment is no reality counter-elemental, and when the environment is no reality counter-elemental, then the environment is no reality elemental. And when the environment is no reality DeepDream, then the environment is no reality counter-DeepDream, and when the environment is no reality counter-DeepDream, then the environment is no reality DeepDream. And when the environment has no reality essence, then the environment has no reality counter-essence, and when the environment has no reality counter-essence, then the environment has no reality essence. And when the environment has no reality position, then the environment has no reality counter-position, and when the environment has no reality counter-position, then the environment has no reality position. And when the environment has no reality moment, then the environment has no reality counter-moment, and when the environment has no reality counter-moment, then the environment has no reality moment. And when the environment has no reality length, then the environment has no reality counter-length, and when the environment has no reality counter-length, then the environment has no reality length. And when the environment has no reality distance, then the environment has no reality counter-distance, and when the environment has no reality counter-distance, then the environment has no reality distance. And when the environment has no reality width, then the environment has no reality counter-width, and when the environment has no reality counter-width, then the environment has no reality width. And when the environment has no reality height, then the environment has no reality counter-height, and when the environment has no reality counter-height, then the environment has no reality height. And when the environment has no reality coordinates, then the environment has no reality counter-coordinates, and when the environment has no reality counter-coordinates, then the environment has no reality coordinates. And when the environment has a no reality map, then the environment has a no reality counter-map, and when the environment has a no reality counter-map, then the environment has a no reality map. And when the environment has no reality dimension, then the environment has no reality counter-dimension, and when the environment has no reality counter-dimension, then the environment has no reality dimension. And when the environment has no reality axis, then the environment has no reality counter-axis, and when the environment has no reality counter-axis, then the environment has no reality axis. And when the environment has a no reality membrane, then the environment has a no reality counter-membrane, and when the environment has a no reality counter-membrane, then the environment has a no reality membrane.

environment has no reality beauty, then the environment has no reality counter-beauty, and when the environment has no reality counter-beauty, then the environment has no reality beauty. And when the environment has a no reality face, then the environment has no reality beauty, and when the environment has no reality beauty, then the environment has a no reality face. And when the environment is no reality up, then the environment is no reality counter-up, and when the environment is no reality counter-up, then the environment is no reality up. And when the environment is no reality down, then the environment is no reality counter-down, and when the environment is no reality counter-down, then the environment is no reality down. And when the environment is no reality left, then the environment is no reality counter-left, and when the environment is no reality counter-left, then the environment is no reality left. And when the environment is no reality right, then the environment is no reality counter-right, and when the environment is no reality counter-right, then the environment is no reality right. And when the environment is no reality forwards, then the environment is no reality counter-forwards, and when the environment is no reality counter-forwards, then the environment is no reality forwards. And when the environment is no reality backwards, then the environment is no reality counter-backwards, and when the environment is no reality counter-backwards, then the environment is no reality backwards. And when the environment has no reality travel, then the environment has no reality zoom, and when the environment has no reality zoom, then the environment has no reality travel. And when the environment has no reality travel, then the environment has no reality counter-travel, and when the environment has no reality counter-travel, then the environment has no reality travel. And when the environment has no reality zoom, then the environment has no reality counter-zoom, and when the environment has no reality counter-zoom, then the environment has no reality zoom. And when the environment has no reality fabric, then the environment has no reality counter-fabric, and when the environment has no reality counter-fabric, then the environment has no reality fabric. And when the environment has no reality space, then the environment has no reality time, and when the environment has no reality time, then the environment has no reality space. And when the environment has no reality space, then the environment has no reality counter-space, and when the environment has no reality counter-space, then the environment has no reality space. And when the environment has no reality time, then the environment has no reality counter-time, and when the environment has no reality counter-time, then the environment has no reality time. And when the environment no reality unchanges, then the environment no reality changes, and when the environment no reality changes, then the environment no reality unchanges. And when the environment no reality changes, then the environment no reality counter-changes, and when the environment no reality counter-changes, then the environment no reality changes. And when the environment no reality unchanges, then the environment no reality counter-unchanges, and when the environment no reality counter-unchanges, then the environment no reality unchanges. And when the environment has no reality space, then the environment has a no reality date, and when the environment has a no reality date, then the environment has no reality space. And when the environment has no reality time, then the environment has a no reality date, and when the environment has a no reality date, then the environment has a no reality counter-date, and when the environment has a no reality counter-date, then the environment has a no reality date. And when the environment has no reality somethingness, then the

environment has no reality nothingness, and when the environment has no reality nothingness, then the environment has no reality somethingness. And when the environment has no reality somethingness, then the environment has no reality counter-somethingness, and when the environment has no reality counter-somethingness, then the environment has no reality somethingness. And when the environment has no reality nothingness, then the environment has no reality counter-nothingness, and when the environment has no reality counter-nothingness, then the environment has no reality nothingness. And when the environment has no reality thingness, then the environment has no reality objectness, and when the environment has no reality objectness, then the environment has no reality thingness. And when the environment has no reality thingness, then the environment has no reality counter-thingness, and when the environment has no reality counter-thingness, then the environment has no reality thingness. And when the environment has no reality objectness, then the environment has no reality counter-objectness, and when the environment has no reality counter-objectness, then the environment has no reality objectness. And when the environment is no reality acid, then the environment is no reality counter-acid, and when the environment is no reality counter-acid, then the environment is no reality acid. And when the environment has no reality objectness, then the environment is no reality acid, and when the environment is no reality acid, then the environment has no reality objectness. And when the environment has no reality thingness, then the environment is no reality acid, and when the environment is no reality acid, then the environment has no reality thingness. And when the environment has no reality location, then the environment has no reality counter-location, and when the environment has no reality counter-location, then the environment has no reality location. And when the environment is no reality positive, then the environment is no reality negative, and when the environment is no reality negative, then the environment is no reality positive. And when the environment is no reality positive, then the environment is no reality counter-positive, and when the environment is no reality counter-positive, then the environment is no reality positive. And when the environment is no reality negative, then the environment is no reality counter-negative, and when the environment is no reality counter-negative, then the environment is no reality negative. And when the environment has a no reality brain, then the environment has a no reality counter-brain, and when the environment has a no reality counter-brain, then the environment has a no reality brain. And when the environment is my no reality extra brain, then the environment is my no reality extra counter-brain, and when the environment is my no reality extra counter-brain, then the environment is my no reality extra brain. And when the environment is no reality imaginary, then the environment is no reality counter-imaginary, and when the environment is no reality counter-imaginary, then the environment is no reality imaginary. And when the environment is no reality inside my head, then the environment is no reality inside my counter-head, and when the environment is no reality inside my counter-head, then the environment is no reality inside my head. And when the environment is no reality cosmic, then the environment is no reality counter-cosmic, and when the environment is no reality counter-cosmic, then the environment is no reality cosmic. And when the environment is no reality mental projection, then the environment is no reality mental counter-projection, and when the environment is no reality mental counter-projection, then the environment is no reality mental projection. And when the environment is no reality hidden, then the environment is no reality seen, and when the environment is no reality seen, then the environment is

no reality hidden. And when the environment is no reality hidden, then the environment is no reality counter-hidden, and when the environment is no reality counter-hidden, then the environment is no reality hidden. And when the environment is no reality seen, then the environment is no reality counter-seen, and when the environment is no reality counter-seen, then the environment is no reality seen. And when there is no reality motion to the environment, then there is no reality counter-motion to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-motion to the environment, then there is no reality motion to the environment. And when the environment has no reality points, then the environment has no reality coordinates, and when the environment has no reality coordinates, then the environment has no reality points. And when the environment has no reality molecules, then the environment has no reality counter-molecules, and when the environment has no reality counter-molecules, then the environment has no reality molecules. And when the environment has no reality chemicals, then the environment has no reality counter-chemicals, and when the environment has no reality counter-chemicals, then the environment has no reality chemicals. And when the environment has no reality dots, then the environment has no reality spots, and when the environment has no reality spots, then the environment has no reality dots. And when the environment has no reality dots, then the environment has no reality counter-dots, and when the environment has no reality counter-dots, then the environment has no reality dots. And when the environment has no reality spots, then the environment has no reality counter-spots, and when the environment has no reality counter-spots, then the environment has no reality spots. And when the environment has no reality elements, then the environment has no reality molecules, and when the environment has no reality molecules, then the environment has no reality elements. And when the environment has no reality molecules, then the environment has no reality chemicals, and when the environment has no reality chemicals, then the environment has no reality molecules. And when the environment no reality morphs, then the environment no reality counter-morphs, and when the environment no reality counter-morphs, then the environment no reality morphs. And when the environment is no reality north, then the environment is no reality south, and when the environment is no reality south, then the environment is no reality north. And when the environment is no reality north, then the environment is no reality east, and when the environment is no reality east, then the environment is no reality north. And when the environment is no reality north, then the environment is no reality west, and when the environment is no reality west, then the environment is no reality north. And when the environment is no reality east, then the environment is no reality west, and when the environment is no reality west, then the environment is no reality east. And when the environment is no reality east, then the environment is no reality north, and when the environment is no reality north, then the environment is no reality east. And when the environment is no reality east, then the environment is no reality south, and when the environment is no reality south, then the environment is no reality east. And when the environment is no reality west, then the environment is no reality north, and when the environment is no reality north, then the environment is no reality west. And when the environment is no reality west, then the environment is no reality east, and when the environment is no reality east, then the environment is no reality west. And when the environment is no reality west, then the environment is no reality south, and when the environment is no reality south, then the environment is no reality west. And when the environment is no reality south, then the environment is no reality north, and when the environment is no reality north, then the

environment is no reality south. And when the environment is no reality south, then the environment is no reality east, and when the environment is no reality east, then the environment is no reality south. And when the environment is no reality south, then the environment is no reality west, and when the environment is no reality west, then the environment is no reality south. And when the environment is no reality north, then the environment is no reality counter-north, and when the environment is no reality counter-north, then the environment is no reality north. And when the environment is no reality east, then the environment is no reality counter-east, and when the environment is no reality counter-east, then the environment is no reality east. And when the environment is no reality west, then the environment is no reality counter-west, and when the environment is no reality counter-west, then the environment is no reality west. And when the environment is no reality south, then the environment is no reality counter-south, and when the environment is no reality counter-south, then the environment is no reality south. And when the environment is a no reality model simulation, then the environment is a no reality model counter-simulation, and when the environment is a no reality model counter-simulation, then the environment is a no reality model simulation. And when there is an no reality eye to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-eye to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-eye to the environment, then there is an no reality eye to the environment. And when there is an no reality ear to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-ear to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-ear to the environment, then there is an no reality ear to the environment. And when there is a no reality mouth to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-mouth to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-mouth to the environment, then there is a no reality mouth to the environment. And when there is a no reality nose to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-nose to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-nose to the environment, then there is a no reality nose to the environment. And when there is a no reality chin to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-chin to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-chin to the environment, then there is a no reality chin to the environment. And when there is a no reality phone plug to the environment, then there is a no reality phone counter-plug to the environment, and when there is a no reality phone counter-plug to the environment, then there is a no reality phone plug to the environment. And when there are no reality illusions, to the environment, then there are no reality counter-illusions to the environment, and when there are no reality counter-illusions to the environment, then there are no reality illusions to the environment. And when there are no reality delusions to the environment, then there are no reality counter-delusions to the environment, and when there are no reality counter-delusions to the environment, then there are no reality delusions to the environment. And when there are no reality grand notions to the environment, then there are no reality grand counter-notions to the environment, and when there are no reality grand counter-notions to the environment, then there are no reality grand notions to the environment. And when there is an no reality extra 4th wall to the environment, then there is an no reality extra 4th counter-wall to the environment, and when there is an no reality extra 4th counter-wall to the environment, then there is an no reality extra 4th wall to the environment. And when there is a no reality horizon to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-horizon to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-horizon to the environment, then there is a no reality horizon to the environment. And when there is no reality recognition to the environment, then there is no reality counter-

recognition to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-recognition to the environment, then there is no reality recognition to the environment. And when there is no reality pondering to the environment, then there is no reality counter-pondering to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-pondering to the environment, then there is no reality pondering to the environment. And when there is no reality identification to the environment, then there is no reality counter-identification to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-identification to the environment, then there is no reality identification to the environment. And when there is no reality perception to the environment, then there is no reality counter-perception to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-perception to the environment, then there is no reality perception to the environment. And when there is no reality reality to the environment, then there is no reality counter-reality to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-reality to the environment, then there is no reality reality to the environment. And when there is no reality reality to the environment, then there is no reality unreality to the environment, and when there is no reality unreality to the environment, then there is no reality reality to the environment. And when there is no reality unreality to the environment, then there is no reality counter-unreality to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-unreality to the environment, then there is no reality unreality to the environment. And when there is no reality synaesthesia to the environment, then there is no reality counter-synaesthesia to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-synaesthesia to the environment, then there is no reality synaesthesia to the environment. And when the environment is no reality in, then the environment is no reality out, and when the environment is no reality out, then the environment is no reality in. And when the environment is no reality in, then the environment is no reality counter-in, and when the environment is no reality counter-in, then the environment is no reality in. And when the environment is no reality out, then the environment is no reality counter-out, and when the environment is no reality counter-out, then the environment is no reality out. And when the environment has no reality scale, then the environment has no reality counter-scale, and when the environment has no reality counter-scale, then the environment has no reality scale. And when the environment has no reality scale, then the environment has no reality unscale, and when the environment has no reality unscale, then the environment has no reality scale. And when the environment has no reality unscale, then the environment has no reality counter-unscale, and when the environment has no reality counter-unscale, then the environment has no reality unscale. And when the environment has no reality depth, then the environment has no reality counter-depth, and when the environment has no reality counter-depth, then the environment has no reality depth. And when the environment has no reality ground, then the environment has no reality warp, and when the environment has no reality warp, then the environment has no reality ground. And when the environment has no reality ground, then the environment has no reality counter-ground, and when the environment has no reality counter-ground, then the environment has no reality ground. And when the environment has no reality warp, then the environment has no reality counter-warp, and when the environment has no reality counter-warp, then the environment has no reality warp. And when the environment has no reality channels, then the environment has no reality counter-channels, and when the environment has no reality counter-channels, then the environment has no reality channels. And when the environment has no reality rabbit holes, then the environment has no reality counter-rabbit holes, and when the

environment has no reality counter-rabbit holes, then the environment has no reality rabbit holes. And when the environment is no reality vividly real, then the environment is no reality vividly counter-real, and when the environment is no reality vividly counter-real, then the environment is no reality real. And when the environment is no reality on, then the environment is no reality off, and when the environment is no reality off, then the environment is no reality on. And when the environment is no reality on, then the environment is no reality counter-on, and when the environment is no reality counter-on, then the environment is no reality on. And when the environment is no reality off, then the environment is no reality counter-off, and when the environment is no reality counter-off, then the environment is no reality off. And when the environment has a no reality switch, then the environment has a no reality counter-switch, and when the environment has a no reality counter-switch, then the environment has a no reality switch. And when the environment has a no reality conversion, then the environment has a no reality counter-conversion, and when the environment has a no reality counter-conversion, then the environment has a no reality conversion. And when the environment has a no reality switch, the environment has a no reality conversion, and when the environment has a no reality conversion, then the environment has a no reality switch. And when the environment has a no reality conversion, then the environment has a no reality switch, and when the environment has a no reality switch, then the environment has a no reality conversion. And when the environment is no reality dream-time, then the environment is no reality hell-time, and when the environment is no reality hell-time, then the environment is no reality dream-time. And when the environment is no reality heaven-time, then the environment is no reality nightmare-time, and when the environment is no reality nightmare-time, then the environment is no reality heaven-time. And when the environment is no reality dream-time, then the environment is no reality heaven-time, and when the environment is no reality heaven-time, then the environment is no reality dream-time. And when the environment is no reality dream-time, then the environment is no reality nightmare-time, and when the environment is no reality nightmare-time, then the environment is no reality dream-time. And when the environment is no reality heaven-time, then the environment is no reality hell-time, and when the environment is no reality hell-time, then the environment is no reality heaven-time. And when the environment is no reality heaven-time, then the environment is no reality counter-heaven-time, and when the environment is no reality counter-heaven-time, then the environment is no reality heaven-time. And when the environment is no reality hell-time, then the environment is no reality counter-hell-time, and when the environment is no reality counter-hell-time, then the environment is no reality hell-time. And when the environment is no reality nightmare-time, then the environment is no reality counter-nightmare-time, and when the environment is no reality counter-nightmare-time, then the environment is no reality nightmare-time. And when the environment is no reality dream-time, then the environment is no reality counter-dream-time, and when the environment is no reality counter-dream-time, then the environment is no reality dream-time. And when the environment is no reality floored, then the environment is no reality ceilinged, and when the environment is no reality ceilinged, then the environment is no reality floored. And when there is a no reality simulator to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-simulator to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-simulator to the environment, then there is a no reality simulator to the environment. And when there is a no reality simulator to the environment, then there is no reality simulating to the environment, and when there is

no reality simulating to the environment, then there is a no reality simulator to the environment. And when there is no reality simulating to the environment, then there is no reality counter-simulating to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-simulating to the environment, then there is no reality simulating to the environment. And when there is no reality simulating to the environment, then there is no reality simulatedness to the environment, and when there is no reality simulatedness to the environment, then there is no reality simulating to the environment. And when there is no reality simulatedness to the environment, then there is no reality counter-simulatedness to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-simulatedness to the environment, then there is no reality simulatedness to the environment. And when there is no reality simulatedness to the environment, then there is no reality portals to the environment, and when there is no reality portals to the environment, then there is no reality simulatedness to the environment. And when there is no reality portals to the environment, then there is no reality simulationedness to the environment, and when there is no reality simulationedness to the environment, then there are no reality portals to the environment. And when there is no reality simulationedness to the environment, then there is no reality counter-simulationedness to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-simulationedness to the environment, then there is no reality simulationedness to the environment. And when there is no reality simulationedness to the environment, then there is a no reality simulator to the environment, and when there is a no reality simulator to the environment, then there is no reality simulationedness to the environment. And when the environment is no reality mental, then the environment is no reality spiritual, and when the environment is no reality spiritual, then the environment is no reality mental. And when the environment is no reality mental, then the environment is no reality counter-mental, and when the environment is no reality counter-mental, then the environment is no reality mental. And when the environment is no reality spiritual, then the environment is no reality counter-spiritual, and when the environment is no reality counter-spiritual, then the environment is no reality spiritual. And when the environment is no reality wonderland, then the environment is no reality counter-wonderland, and when the environment is no reality counter-wonderland, then the environment is no reality wonderland. And when the environment is no reality stable, then the environment is no reality unstable, and when the environment is no reality unstable, then the environment is no reality stable. And when the environment is no reality stable, then the environment is no reality counter-stable, and when the environment is no reality counter-stable, then the environment is no reality stable. And when the environment is no reality unstable, then the environment is no reality counter-unstable, and when the environment is no reality counter-unstable, then the environment is no reality unstable. And when the environment is no reality forever sleeping, then the environment is no reality forever counter-sleeping, and when the environment is no reality forever counter-sleeping, then the environment is no reality forever sleeping. And when the environment is no reality never awake, then the environment is no reality forever sleeping, and when the environment is no reality forever sleeping, then the environment is no reality never awake. And when the environment is no reality never awake, then the environment is no reality never counter-awake, and when the environment is no reality never counter-awake, then the environment is no reality never awake. And when I am no reality forever sleeping, then I am no reality forever counter-sleeping, and when I am no reality forever counter-sleeping, then I am no reality forever sleeping. And when I am no reality never awake,

then I am no reality forever sleeping, and when I am no reality forever sleeping, then I am no reality never awake. And when I am no reality never awake, then I am no reality never counter-awake, and when I am no reality never counter-awake, then I am no reality never awake. And when the environment is no reality final, then the environment is no reality counter-final, and when the environment is no reality counter-final, then the environment is no reality final. And when the environment has no reality relatedness, then the environment has no reality unrelatedness, and when the environment has no reality unrelatedness, then the environment has no reality relatedness. And when the environment has no reality relatedness, then the environment has no reality counter-relatedness, and when the environment has no reality counter-relatedness, then the environment has no reality relatedness. And when the environment has no reality unrelatedness, then the environment has no reality counter-unrelatedness, and when the environment has no reality counter-unrelatedness, then the environment has no reality unrelatedness. And when the environment has no reality sameness, then the environment has no reality differentness, and when the environment has no reality differentness, then the environment has no reality sameness. And when the environment has no reality sameness, then the environment has no reality counter-sameness, and when the environment has no reality counter-sameness, then the environment has no reality sameness. And when the environment has no reality differentness, then the environment has no reality counter-differentness, and when the environment has no reality counter-differentness, then the environment has no reality differentness. And when the environment gets no reality installed, then the environment gets no reality uninstalled, and when the environment gets no reality uninstalled, then the environment gets no reality installed. And when the environment gets no reality installed, then the environment gets no reality counter-installed, and when the environment gets no reality counter-installed, then the environment gets no reality installed. And when the environment gets no reality uninstalled, then the environment gets no reality counter-uninstalled, and when the environment gets no reality counter-uninstalled, then the environment gets no reality uninstalled. And when the environment is no reality aware, then the environment is no reality unaware, and when the environment is no reality unaware, then the environment is no reality aware. And when the environment is no reality aware, then the environment is no reality counter-aware, and when the environment is no reality counter-aware, then the environment is no reality aware. And when the environment is no reality unaware, then the environment is no reality counter-unaware, and when the environment is no reality counter-unaware, then the environment is no reality unaware. And when there are no reality characters of the dream-time environment, then there are no reality counter-characters of the dream-time environment, and when there are no reality counter-characts of the dream-time environment, then there are no reality characters of the dream-time environment. And when there is a no reality setting to the dream-time environment, then there is a no reality counter-setting to the dream-time environment, and when there is a no reality counter-setting to the dream-time environment, then there is a no reality setting to the dream-time environment. And when there is no reality personality to the environment, then there is no reality counter-personality to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-personality to the environment, then there is no reality personality to the environment. And when there is no reality aspects to the environment, then there is no reality counter-aspects to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-aspects to the environment, then there is no reality aspects to the environment. And

when there is no reality effects of the environment, then there is no reality counter-effects of the environment, and when there is no reality counter-effects of the environment, then there is no reality effects of the environment. And when the environment is no reality hummified, then the environment is no reality counter-hummified, and when the environment is no reality counter-hummified, then the environment is no reality hummified. And when the environment is no reality hummified, then the environment is no reality unhummed, and when the environment is no reality unhummed, then the environment is no reality hummified. And when the environment is no reality unhummed, then the environment is no reality counter-unhummed, and when the environment is no reality counter-unhummed, then the environment is no reality unhummed. And when the environment is no reality thoughts, then the environment is no reality unthoughts, and when the environment is no reality unthoughts, then the environment is no reality thoughts. And when the environment is no reality thoughts, then the environment is no reality counter-thoughts, and when the environment is no reality counter-thoughts, then the environment is no reality thoughts. And when the environment is no reality unthoughts, then the environment is no reality counter-unthoughts, and when the environment is no reality counter-unthoughts, then the environment is no reality unthoughts. And when the environment is no reality language, then the environment is no reality linguistics, and when the environment is no reality linguistics, then the environment is no reality language. And when the environment is no reality language, then the environment is no reality counter-language, and when the environment is no reality counter-language, then the environment is no reality language. And when the environment is no reality linguistics, then the environment is no reality counter-linguistics, and when the environment is no reality counter-linguistics, then the environment is no reality linguistics. And when the environment is no reality someone, then the environment is no reality no-one, and when the environment no reality is no-one, then the environment is no reality someone. And when the environment is no reality someone, then the environment is no reality counter-someone, and when the environment is no reality counter-someone, then the environment is no reality someone. And when the environment is no reality no-one, then the environment is no reality counter-no-one, and when the environment is no reality counter-no-one, then the environment is no reality no-one. And when the environment is no reality unned, then the environment is no reality counter-unned, and when the environment is no reality counter-unned, then the environment is no reality unned. And when the environment is no reality information, then the environment is no reality uninformation, and when the environment is no reality uninformation, then the environment is no reality information. And when the environment is no reality information, then the environment is no reality counter-information, and when the environment is no reality counter-information, then the environment is no reality information. And when the environment is no reality uninformation, then the environment is no reality counter-uninformation, and when the environment is no reality counter-uninformation, then the environment is no reality uninformation. And when the environment is no reality communication, then the environment is no reality uncommunication, and when the environment is no reality uncommunication, then the environment is no reality communication. And when the environment is no reality communication, then the environment is no reality counter-communication, and when the environment is no reality counter-communication, then the environment is no reality communication. And when the environment is no reality uncommunication, then the

environment is no reality counter-uncommunication, and when the environment is no reality counter-uncommunication, then the environment is no reality uncommunication. And when the environment has no reality feelings, then the environment has no reality unfeelings, and when the environment has no reality unfeelings, then the environment has no reality feelings. And when the environment has no reality feelings, then the environment has no reality counter-feelings, and when the environment has no reality counter-feelings, then the environment has no reality feelings. And when the environment has no reality unfeelings, then the environment has no reality counter-unfeelings, and when the environment has no reality counter-unfeelings, then the environment has no reality unfeelings. And when the environment has no reality emotions, then the environment has no reality unemotions, and when the environment has no reality unemotions, then the environment has no reality emotions. And when the environment has emotions, then the environment has counter-emotions, and when the environment has counter-emotions, then the environment has no reality emotions. And when the environment has no reality unemotions, then the environment has no reality counter-unemotions, and when the environment has no reality counter-unemotions, then the environment has no reality unemotions. And when the environment is no reality ghosted, then the environment is no reality counter-ghosted, and when the environment is no reality counter-ghosted, then the environment is no reality ghosted. And when the environment is no reality ghosted, then the environment is no reality unghosted, and when the environment is no reality unghosted, then the environment is no reality ghosted. And when the environment is no reality unghosted, then the environment is no reality counter-unghosted, and when the environment is no reality counter-unghosted, then the environment is no reality unghosted. And when the environment is no reality ghosted, then the environment is no reality dream-time, and when the environment is no reality no reality dream-time, then the environment is ghosted. And when the environment is no reality dream-time, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality dream-time. And when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-dreams, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams. And when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens facts, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens facts, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams. And when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-facts, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-facts, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams. And when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens fiction, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens fiction, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams. And when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-fiction, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-fiction, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams. And when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens truth, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens truth, then the environment is no

reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams. And when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-truth, and when the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens counter-truth, then the environment is no reality Lachlan (Lilly) Maddens dreams. And when the environment is a no reality dream-time rabbithole, then the environment is a no reality dream-time counter-rabbithole, and when the environment is a no reality dream-time counter-rabbithole, then the environment is a no reality dream-time rabbithole. And when the environment is no reality fractioned, then the environment is no reality counter-fractioned, and when the environment is no reality counter-fractioned, then the environment is no reality fractioned. And when the environment is no reality mythical, then the environment is no reality legendary, and when the environment is no reality legendary, then the environment is no reality mythical. And when the environment is no reality mythical, then the environment is no reality unmythical, and when the environment is no reality unmythical, then the environment is no reality mythical. And when the environment is no reality mythical, then the environment is no reality counter-mythical, and when the environment is no reality counter-mythical, then the environment is no reality mythical. And when the environment is no reality unmythical, then the environment is no reality counter-unmythical, and when the environment is no reality counter-unmythical, then the environment is no reality unmythical. And when the environment is no reality legendary, then the environment is no reality unlegendary, and when the environment is no reality unlegendary, then the environment is no reality legendary. And when the environment is no reality legendary, then the environment is no reality counter-legendary, and when the environment is no reality counter-legendary, then the environment is no reality legendary. And when the environment is no reality unlegendary, then the environment is no reality counter-unlegendary, and when the environment is no reality counter-unlegendary, then the environment is no reality unlegendary. And when the environment is no reality natural, then the environment is no reality supernatural, and when the environment is no reality supernatural, then the environment is no reality natural. And when the environment is no reality natural, then the environment is no reality unnatural, and when the environment is no reality unnatural, then the environment is no reality natural. And when the environment is no reality natural, then the environment is no reality counter-natural, and when the environment is no reality counter-natural, then the environment is no reality natural. And when the environment is no reality unnatural, then the environment is no reality counter-unnatural, and when the environment is no reality counter-unnatural, then the environment is no reality unnatural. And when the environment is no reality supernatural, then the environment is no reality unsupernatural, and when the environment is no reality unsupernatural, then the environment is no reality supernatural. And when the environment is no reality supernatural, then the environment is no reality counter-supernatural, and when the environment is no reality counter-supernatural, then the environment is no reality supernatural. And when the environment is no reality unsupernatural, then the environment is no reality counter-unsupernatural, and when the environment is no reality counter-unsupernatural, then the environment is no reality unsupernatural. And when the environment is no reality somewhere, then the environment is no reality nowhere, and when the environment is no reality nowhere, then the environment is no reality somewhere. And when the environment is no reality somewhere, then the environment is no reality counter-somewhere, and when the environment is no reality counter-somewhere, then the

environment is no reality somewhere. And when the environment is no reality nowhere, then the environment is no reality counter-nowhere, and when the environment is no reality counter-nowhere, then the environment is no reality nowhere. And when no reality outsideness is inside the environment, then no reality outsideness is beyond the horizon of the environment, and when no reality outsideness is beyond the horizon of the environment, then no reality outsideness is inside the environment. And when the no reality environment is something seen, then the no reality environment is nothing seen, and when the no reality environment is nothing seen, then the no reality environment is something seen. And when the no reality environment is something seen, then the no reality environment is something hidden, and when the no reality environment is something hidden, then the no reality environment is something seen. And when the no reality environment is nothing seen, then the no reality environment is nothing hidden, and when the no reality environment is nothing hidden, then the no reality environment is nothing seen. And when the environment is no reality clever, then the environment is no reality retardation, and when the environment is no reality retardation, then the environment is no reality clever. And when the environment is no reality clever, then the environment is no reality unclever, and when the environment is no reality unclever, then the environment is no reality clever. And when the environment is no reality clever, then the environment is no reality counter-clever, and when the environment is no reality counter-clever, then the environment is no reality clever. And when the environment is no reality unclever, then the environment is no reality counter-unclever, and when the environment is no reality counter-unclever, then the environment is no reality unclever. And when the environment is no reality retardation, then the environment is no reality unretardation, and when the environment is no reality unretardation, then the environment is no reality retardation. And when the environment is no reality retardation, then the environment is no reality counter-retardation, and when the environment is no reality counter-retardation, then the environment is no reality retardation. And when the environment is no reality unretardation, then the environment is no reality counter-unretardation, and when the environment is no reality counter-unretardation, then the environment is no reality unretardation. And when there is no reality no time in the environment, then there is a no reality root of time in the environment, and when there is a no reality root of time in the environment, then there is no reality no time in the environment. And when there are no reality plant roots in the environment, then there are no reality roots of time in the environment, and when there are no reality roots of time in the environment, then there is no reality plant roots in the environment. And when there is no reality no time in the environment, then there is no reality counter-no time in the environment, and when there is no reality counter-no time in the environment, then there is no reality no time in the environment. And when there is a no reality root of time in the environment, then there is a no reality fraction of time in the environment, and when there is a no reality fraction of time in the environment, then there is a no reality root of time in the environment. And when there is a no reality root of time in the environment, then there is a no reality counter-root of time in the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-root of time in the environment, then there is a no reality root of time in the environment. And when there is a no reality fraction of time in the environment, then there is a no reality counter-fraction of time in the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-fraction of time in the environment, then there is a no reality fraction of time in the environment. And when there is a no reality fraction of time in the environment, then there is a no reality moment

there is a no reality month of time in the environment, then there is a no reality week of time in the environment. And when there is a no reality month of time in the environment, then there is a no reality counter-month of time in the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-month of time in the environment, then there is a no reality month of time in the environment. And when there is a no reality month of time in the environment, then there is a no reality year of time in the environment, and when there is a no reality year of time in the environment, then there is a no reality month of time in the environment. And when there is a no reality year of time in the environment, then there is a no reality counter-year of time in the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-year of time in the environment, then there is a no reality year of time in the environment. And when there is no reality time in the environment, then the environment is no reality vividly lucid psychedelia, and when the environment is no reality vividly lucid psychedelia, then there is no reality time in the environment. And when there is a no reality painting to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-painting to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-painting to the environment, then there is a no reality painting to the environment. And when there is a no reality painting to the environment, then there is a no reality portrait to the environment, and when there is a no reality portrait to the environment, then there is a no reality painting to the environment. And when there is a no reality portrait to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-portrait to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-portrait to the environment, then there is a no reality portrait to the environment. And when there is a no reality painting to the environment, then there is a no reality landscape to the environment, and when there is a no reality landscape to the environment, then there is a no reality portrait to the environment. And when there is a no reality landscape to the environment, then there is a no reality counter-landscape to the environment, and when there is a no reality counter-landscape to the environment, then there is a no reality landscape to the environment. And when there is a no reality painting to the environment, then there are no reality outlines to the environment, and when there are no reality outlines to the environment, then there is a no reality painting to the environment. And when there are no reality outlines to the environment, then there are no reality counter-outlines to the environment, and when there are no reality counter-outlines to the environment, then there are no reality outlines to the environment. And when there is a no reality painting to the environment, then there is no reality still-motion to the environment, and when there is no reality still-motion to the environment, then there is a no reality painting to the environment. And when there is no reality still-motion to the environment, then there is no reality counter-still-motion to the environment, and when there is no reality counter-still-motion to the environment, then there is no reality still-motion to the environment. And when the environment is no reality strange, then the environment is no reality weird, and when the environment is no reality weird, then the environment is no reality strange. And when the environment is no reality atomic, then the environment is no reality unatomic, and when the environment is no reality unatomic, then the environment is no reality atomic. And when the environment is no reality atomic, then the environment is no reality counter-atomic, and when the environment is no reality counter-atomic, then the environment is no reality atomic. And when the environment is no reality unatomic, then the environment is no reality counter-unatomic, and when the environment is no reality counter-unatomic, then the environment is no reality unatomic. And when the environment is no reality complete, then the environment is no

reality incomplete, and when the environment is no reality incomplete, then the environment is no reality complete. And when the environment is no reality complete, then the environment is no reality counter-complete, and when the environment is no reality counter-complete, then the environment is no reality complete. And when the environment is no reality incomplete, then the environment is no reality counter-incomplete, and when the environment is no reality counter-incomplete, then the environment is no reality incomplete. And when the environment is no reality absolute, then the environment is no reality inabsolute, and when the environment is no reality inabsolute, then the environment is no reality absolute. And when the environment is no reality absolute, then the environment is no reality counter-absolute, and when the environment is no reality counter-absolute, then the environment is no reality absolute. And when the environment is no reality inabsolute, then the environment is c no reality ounter-inabsolute, and when the environment is no reality counter-inabsolute, then the environment is no reality inabsolute. And when the environment of no reality gardenlands is behind a mirror, then the environment of no reality gardenlands is behind a counter-mirror, and when the environment of no reality gardenlands is behind a counter-mirror, then the environment of no reality gardenlands is behind a mirror. And when the environment of no reality gardenlands puts people to sleep, then the environment of no reality gardenlands causes people to experience counter-sleep, and when the environment of no reality gardenlands causes people to experience counter-sleep, then the environment of no reality gardenlands puts people to sleep. And when the environment of no reality gardenlands makes people never wake up, then the environment of no reality gardenlands makes people never counter-wake up, and when the environment of no reality gardenlands makes people never counter-wake up, then the environment of no reality gardenlands makes people never wake up. When something about the environment no reality exists, then nothing about the environment no reality exists, and when nothing about the environment no reality exists, then something about the environment no reality exists. And when the environment is no reality somewhere in the world of attoria, then the environment is no reality nowhere in the world of attoria, and when the environment is no reality nowhere in the world of attoria, then the environment is no reality somewhere in the world of attoria. And when the environment is no reality somewhere on planet promethia, then the environment is no reality nowhere on the planet promethia, and when the environment is no reality nowhere on the planet of promethia, then the environment is no reality somewhere on the planet promethia. And when the environment has no reality value, then the environment has no reality unvalue, and when the environment has no reality unvalue, then the environment has no reality value. And when the environment has no reality value, then the environment has no reality counter-value, and when the environment has no reality counter-value, then the environment has no reality value. And when the environment has no reality unvalue, then the environment has no reality counter-unvalue, and when the environment has no reality counter-unvalue, then the environment has no reality unvalue. And when the environment has no reality dimensions, then the environment has no reality undimensions, and when the environment has no reality undimensions, then the environment has no reality dimensions. And when the environment has no reality undimensions, then the environment has no reality counter-undimensions, and when the environment has no reality counter-undimensions, then the environment has no reality undimensions. And when the environment has no reality matter, then the environment has no reality

unmatter, and when the environment has no reality unmatter, then the environment has no reality matter. And when the environment has no reality matter, then the environment has no reality counter-matter, and when the environment has no reality counter-matter, then the environment has no reality matter. And when the environment has no reality unmatter, then the environment has no reality counter-unmatter, and when the environment has no reality counter-unmatter, then the environment has no reality unmatter. And when the environment has a no reality verse, then the environment has a no reality counter-verse, and when the environment has a no reality counter-verse, then the environment has a no reality verse. And when the environment has no reality set layers, then the environment has no reality counter-set layers, and when the environment has no reality counter-set layers, then the environment has no reality set layers. When the environment has a no reality forceless force, then the environment has a no reality counter forceless force, and when the environment has a no reality counter forceless force, then the environment has a no reality forceless force. And when there are no reality force mechanics for the environment, then there are no reality force counter mechanics for the environment, and when there are no reality force counter mechanics for the environment, then there are no reality force mechanics for the environment. And when there is a no reality mirror plane for the environment, then there is a no reality mirror counter-plane for the environment, and when there is a no reality mirror counter-plane for the environment, then there is a no reality mirror plane for the environment. And when the environment has no reality quality, then the environment has no reality unquality, and when the environment has no reality unquality, then the environment has no reality quality. And when the environment has no reality quality, then the environment has no reality counter-quality, and when the environment has no reality counter-quality, then the environment has no reality quality. And when the environment has no reality unquality, then the environment has no reality counter-unquality, and when the environment has no reality counter-unquality, then the environment has no reality unquality. And when the environment is no reality behind times root, then the environment is no reality behind times counter-root, and when the environment is no reality behind times counter-root, then the environment is no reality behind times root. And when the environment is no reality non-everything, then the environment is no reality non-counter-everything, and when the environment is no reality non-counter-everything, then the environment is no reality non-everything. And when the environment is no reality non-anything, then the environment is no reality non-counter-anything, and when the environment is no reality non-counter-anything, then the environment is no reality non-anything. And when the environment is no reality vividly lucid, then the environment is no reality vividly unlucid, and when the environment is no reality vividly unlucid, then the environment is no reality vividly lucid. And when the environment is no reality vividly lucid, then the environment is no reality vividly counter-lucid, and when the environment is no reality vividly counter-lucid, then the environment is no reality vividly lucid. And when the environment is no reality vividly unlucid, then the environment is no reality vividly counter-unlucid, and when the environment is no reality vividly counter-unlucid, then the environment is no reality vividly unlucid. And when the environment is no reality mind matter, then the environment is no reality mind counter-matter, and when the environment is no reality mind counter-matter, then the environment is no reality mind matter. And when the environment is no reality non-physical, then the environment is no reality non-counter-physical, and when the environment is no reality non-counter-physical, then the

environment is no reality non-physical. And when the environment has no reality non-memory, then the environment no reality remembers, and when the environment no reality remembers, then the environment has no reality non-memory. And when the environment is no reality fused, then the environment is no reality split, and when the environment is no reality split, then the environment is no reality fused. And when the environment is no reality fused, then the environment is no reality unfused, and when the environment is no reality unfused, then the environment is no reality fused. And when the environment is no reality fused, then the environment is no reality counter-fused, and when the environment is no reality counter-fused, then the environment is no reality fused. And when the environment is no reality unfused, then the environment is no reality counter-unfused, and when the environment is no reality counter-unfused, then the environment is no reality unfused. And when the environment is no reality split, then the environment is no reality unsplit, and when the environment is no reality unsplit, then the environment is no reality split. And when the environment is no reality split, then the environment is no reality counter-split, and when the environment is no reality counter-split, then the environment is no reality split. And when the environment is no reality unsplit, then the environment is no reality counter-unsplit, and when the environment is no reality counter-unsplit, then the environment is no reality unsplit. And when the environment is wedged in a no reality absolutely completely perpetually finally white moon mirror moon gold pure somewhere Lokis environment nature environment Lokis somewhere pure silver moon mirror moon white finally perpetually completely absolutely, then the environment is wedged in a no reality absolutely completely perpetually finally white moon mirror moon gold pure nowhere Lokis environment LSD environment Lokis nowhere pure silver moon mirror moon white finally perpetually completely absolutely, and when the environment is wedged in a no reality absolutely completely perpetually finally white moon mirror moon gold pure nowhere Lokis environment LSD environment Lokis nowhere pure silver moon mirror moon white finally perpetually completely absolutely, then the environment is wedged in a no reality absolutely completely perpetually finally white moon mirror moon gold pure somewhere Lokis environment nature environment Lokis somewhere pure silver moon mirror moon white finally perpetually completely absolutely. And when the environment is no reality televised, then the environment is no reality video'd, and when the environment is no reality video'd, then the environment is no reality televised. And when the environment is no reality video'd, then the environment is no reality cinematic, and when the environment is no reality cinematic, then the environment is no reality video'd. And when the environment is no reality believable, then the environment is no reality unbelievable, and when the environment is no reality unbelievable, then the environment is no reality believable. And when the environment is no reality believable, then the environment is no reality counter-believable, and when the environment is no reality counter-believable, then the environment is no reality believable. And when the environment is no reality unbelievable, then the environment is no reality counter-unbelievable, and when the environment is no reality counter-unbelievable, then the environment is no reality unbelievable. And when the environment is no reality perpetual, then the environment is no reality unperpetual, and when the environment is no reality unperpetual, then the environment is no reality perpetual. And when the environment is no reality perpetual, then the environment is no reality counter-perpetual, and when the environment is no reality counter-perpetual, then the environment is no reality

perpetual. And when the environment is no reality unperpetual, then the environment is no reality counter-unperpetual, and when the environment is no reality counter-unperpetual, then the environment is no reality unperpetual. And when the environment is no reality perpetual, then the environment is no reality constant, and when the environment is no reality constant, then the environment is no reality perpetual. And when the environment is no reality constant, then the environment is no reality unconstant, and when the environment is no reality unconstant, then the environment is no reality constant. And when the environment is no reality constant, then the environment is no reality counter-constant, and when the environment is no reality counter-constant, then the environment is no reality constant. And when the environment is no reality unconstant, then the environment is no reality counter-unconstant, and when the environment is no reality counter-unconstant, then the environment is no reality unconstant. And when the environment is a no reality changing illusion, then the environment is a no reality changing counter-illusion, and when the environment is a no reality changing counter-illusion, then the environment is a no reality changing illusion. And when the environment is a no reality united season, then the environment is a no reality united counter-season, and when the environment is a no reality united counter-season, then the environment is a no reality united season. And when the environment has the essence of no reality LSD, then the environment has the essence of no reality counter-LSD, and when the environment has the essence of no reality counter-LSD, then the environment has the essence of no reality LSD. When the environment is the no reality 0th environment, then the environment is the no reality 0th counter-environment, and when the environment is the no reality 0th counter-environment, then the environment is the no reality 0th environment. And when the no reality 0th environment is the nothing environment, then the no reality minus one environment is the something environment, and when the no reality minus one environment is the something environment, then the no reality 0th environment is the nothing environment. And when the environment is the no reality either environment, then the environment is the no reality both environment, and when the environment is the no reality both environment, then the environment is the no reality either environment. And when the environment is the no reality neither environment, then the environment is the no reality rather environment, and when the environment is the no reality rather environment, then the environment is the no reality neither environment. And when the environment is the no reality final thing, then the environment is the no reality final counter-thing, and when the environment is the no reality final counter-thing, then the environment is the no reality final thing. And when the environment is the no reality final object, then the environment is the no reality final counter-object, and when the environment is the no reality final counter-object, then the environment is the no reality final object. And when the environment is the no reality final thing, then the environment is the no reality final object, and when the environment is the no reality final object, then the environment is the no reality final thing. And when the environment is no reality 2D+2ExtraD, then the environment is no reality counter-2D+2ExtraD, and when the environment is no reality counter-2D+2ExtraD, then the environment is no reality 2D+2ExtraD. And when the environment is no reality one thing, then the environment is no reality counter-one thing, and when the environment is no reality counter-one thing, then the environment is no reality one thing. And when the environment no reality knows, then the environment no reality counter-knows, and when the environment no reality counter-knows, then the environment no reality knows. And

when the environment is the no reality nothingness of a nightmare, then the environment is the no reality somethingness of a dream, and when the environment is the no reality somethingness of a dream, then the environment is the no reality nothingness of a nightmare. And when the environment is the no reality nothingness of hell, then the environment is the no reality somethingness of heaven, and when the environment is the no reality somethingness of heaven, then the environment is the no reality nothingness of hell. And when the environment is no reality nothinged nothingness, then the environment is no reality somethinged somethingness, and when the environment is no reality somethinged somethingness, then the environment is no reality nothinged nothingness. And when the environment is no reality nothinged nothingness, then the environment is no reality nothinged counter-nothingness, and when the environment is no reality nothinged counter-nothingness, then the environment is no reality nothinged nothingness. And when the environment is no reality somethinged somethingness, then the environment is no reality somethinged counter-somethingness, and when the environment is no reality somethinged counter-somethingness, then the environment is no reality somethinged somethingness. And when nothing of the no reality environment remembers, then something of the no reality environment remembers, and when something of the no reality environment remembers, then nothing of the no reality environment remembers. And when something about the environment is no reality unstable yet stable, then nothing about the environment is no reality dis-stable yet mis-stable, and when nothing about the environment is no reality dis-stable yet mis-stable, then something about the environment is no reality unstable yet stable. And when the environment has a no reality meltdown, then the environment has a no reality counter-meltdown, and when the environment has a no reality counter-meltdown, then the environment has a no reality meltdown. And when something about the environment is no reality 00, then something about the environment becomes no reality 01, and when something about the environment becomes no reality 01, then something about the environment is no reality 00. And when the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of information, then the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-information, and when the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-information, then reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum information. And when reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-information, then reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of dis-information, and when reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of dis-information, then reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-information. And when the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of communication, then reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-communication, and when reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-communication, then the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of communication. And when the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-communication, then the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of dis-communication, and when the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of dis-communication, then the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-communication. And when the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of language, then the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-language, and when the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of mis-language, then the reality of the environment is the no reality spectrum of language. And when the reality of the

of the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-mimes, then reality of the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-mimes. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet vision, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet mis-vision, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet mis-vision, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet vision. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet mis-vision, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet dis-vision, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet dis-vision, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality ultraviolet mis-vision. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality fractals, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-fractals, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-fractals, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality fractals. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-fractals, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-fractals, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-fractals, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-fractals. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality hallucinations, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-hallucinations, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-hallucinations, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-hallucinations, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-hallucinations, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-hallucinations. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality psychedelia, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-psychedelia, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-psychedelia, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality psychedelia. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-psychedelia, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-psychedelia, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-psychedelia, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-psychedelia. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality alterdness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-alterdness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-alterdness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality alterdness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-alterdness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-alterdness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-alterdness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-alterdness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality non-scientificness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality non-mis-scientificness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality non-mis-scientificness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality non-dis-scientificness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality non-dis-scientificness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality non-mis-scientificness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear possibilities, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear mis-possibilities, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear mis-possibilities, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear possibilities. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear mis-possibilities, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear dis-possibilities, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear dis-possibilities, then

the environment is the spectrum of no reality nuclear mis-possibilities. And when the environment is dated as the no reality nuclear 60's, then the environment is dated as the no reality nuclear counter-60's, and when the environment is dated as the no reality nuclear counter-60's, then the environment is dated as the no reality nuclear 60's. And when the environment is home to the no reality old Norse, then the environment is home to the no reality old counter-Norse, and when the environment is home to the no reality old counter-Norse, then the environment is home to the no reality old Norse. And when the environment is experiencing the spectrum of an no reality acid-wash, then the environment is experiencing the spectrum of a no reality acid-counter-wash, and when the environment is experiencing the spectrum of a no reality acid-counter-wash, then the environment is experiencing the spectrum of an no reality acid-wash. And when the environment has the spectrum of no reality noise, then the environment has the spectrum of no reality mis-noise, and when the environment has the spectrum of no reality mis-noise, then the environment has the spectrum of no reality noise. And when the environment has the spectrum of no reality mis-noise, then the environment has the spectrum of no reality dis-noise, and when the environment has the spectrum of no reality dis-noise, then the environment has the spectrum of no reality mis-noise. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality expectation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-expectation, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-expectation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality expectation. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-expectation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-expectation, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-expectation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-expectation. And when the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality dream-time, then the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality mis-dream-time, and when the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality mis-dream-time, then the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality dream-time. And when the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality mis-dream-time, then the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality dis-dream-time, and when the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality dis-dream-time, then the environment is the spectrum of layers of no reality mis-dream-time. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality coherency, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-coherency, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-coherency, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality coherency. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-coherency, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-coherency, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-coherency, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-coherency. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-looks, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-mis-looks, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-mis-looks, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-looks. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-mis-looks, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-dis-looks, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-dis-looks, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality thought-mis-looks. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality seenness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-seenness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-seenness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality seenness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-seenness, then the environment

dreamscape. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality happening, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-happening, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-happening, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality happening. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-happening, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-happening, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-happening, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-happening. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality something, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-something, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-something, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality something. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-something, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-something, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-something, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-something. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality nothing, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-nothing, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-nothing, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality nothing. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-nothing, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-nothing, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-nothing, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-nothing. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear meltdown, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear mis-meltdown, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear mis-meltdown, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear meltdown. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear mis-meltdown, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear dis-meltdown, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear dis-meltdown, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality nuclear mis-meltdown. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality map, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality mis-map, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality mis-map, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality map. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality mis-map, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality dis-map, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality dis-map, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality mis-map. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality installation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-installation, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-installation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality installation. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-installation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-installation, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-installation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-installation. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality activation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-activation, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-activation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality activation. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-activation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-activation, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-activation, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-activation. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality psychedelic wonderland, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality psychedelic mis-wonderland, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality

psychedelic mis-wonderland, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality
psychedelic wonderland. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality
psychedelic mis-wonderland, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality
psychedelic dis-wonderland, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality
psychedelic dis-wonderland, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality
psychedelic mis-wonderland. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality
fusion, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-fusion, and when the
environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-fusion, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality fusion. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality
mis-fusion, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-fusion, and when the
environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-fusion, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality mis-fusion. And when the environment is the spectrum of no
reality splitness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-splitness, and
when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-splitness, then the environment
is the spectrum of no reality splitness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no
reality mis-splitness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-splitness,
and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-splitness, then the
environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-splitness. And when the environment is
the spectrum of no reality synaesthetic experience, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality synaesthetic mis-experience, and when the environment is the
spectrum of no reality synaesthetic mis-experience, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality synaesthetic experience. And when the environment is the
spectrum of no reality synaesthetic mis-experience, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality synaesthetic dis-experience, and when the environment is the
spectrum of no reality synaesthetic dis-experience, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality synaesthetic mis-experience. And when the environment is the
spectrum of no reality age, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-age,
and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-age, then the environment
is the spectrum of no reality age. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality
mis-age, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-age, and when the
environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-age, then the environment is the spectrum
of no reality mis-age. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality zooming,
then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-zooming, and when the
environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-zooming, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality zooming. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality
mis-zooming, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-zooming, and when
the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-zooming, then the environment is the
spectrum of no reality mis-zooming. And when the environment is the spectrum of no
reality imaginary figments, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality imaginary
mis-figments, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality imaginary mis-
figments, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality imaginary figments. And
when the environment is the spectrum of no reality imaginary mis-figments, then the
environment is the spectrum of no reality imaginary dis-figments, and when the
environment is the spectrum of no reality imaginary dis-figments, then the environment
is the spectrum of no reality imaginary mis-figments. And when the future of the
environment remembers the no reality past, then the past of the environment forgets the
no reality future, and when the past of the environment forgets the no reality future,
then the future of the environment remembers the no reality past. And when the present of

the environment is the no reality fixed past, then the present of the environment is the no reality flexible future, and when the present of the environment is the no reality flexible future, then the present of the environment is the no reality fixed past. And when the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum energy, then the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum mis-energy, and when the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum mis-energy, then the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum energy. And when the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum mis-energy, then the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum dis-energy, and when the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum dis-energy, then the environment has the essence of no reality eternal quantum mis-energy. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra brain, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra mis-brain, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra mis-brain, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra brain. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra mis-brain, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra dis-brain, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra dis-brain, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality magical extra mis-brain. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical emotions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-emotions, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-emotions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical emotions. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-emotions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-emotions, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-emotions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-emotions. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical feelings, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-feelings, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-feelings, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical feelings. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-feelings, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-feelings, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-feelings, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-feelings. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical expressions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-expressions, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-expressions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical expressions. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-expressions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-expressions, and when the environment is the expression of no reality magical dis-expressions, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-expressions. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical senses, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-senses, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-senses, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical senses. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-senses, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-senses, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-senses, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-senses. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical meaning, then the environment is the

spectrum of no reality magical mis-meaning, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-meaning, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical meaning. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-meaning, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-meaning, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-meaning, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-meaning. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply revealed, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply mis-revealed, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply mis-revealed, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply revealed. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply mis-revealed, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply dis-revealed, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply dis-revealed, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality something deeply mis-revealed. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality apparently, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality actually, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality actually, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality apparently. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical awareness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-awareness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-awareness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical awareness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-awareness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-awareness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-awareness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-awareness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical beliefs, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-beliefs, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-beliefs, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical beliefs. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-beliefs, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-beliefs, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-beliefs, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-beliefs. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical powers, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-powers, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-powers, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical powers. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-powers, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-powers, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-powers, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-powers. And when the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical brains, then the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-brains, and when the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-brains, then the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical brains. And when the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-brains, then the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-brains, and when the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-brains, then the environmental brain is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-brains. And when the environment gives a no reality magical brain, then the environment borrows a no reality magical brain, and when the environment borrows a no reality magical brain, then the

environment gives a no reality magical brain. And when the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical force, then the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical mis-force, and when the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical mis-force, then the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical force. And when the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical mis-force, then the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical dis-force, and when the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical dis-force, then the environment is the spectrum of the no reality magical mis-force. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical hypnosis, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-hypnosis, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-hypnosis, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical hypnosis. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-hypnosis, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-hypnosis, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-hypnosis, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-hypnosis. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical psychology, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-psychology, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-psychology, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical psychology. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-psychology, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-psychology, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical dis-psychology, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality magical mis-psychology. And when gardenlands is no reality somewhere Minnesota, then gardenlands is no reality nowhere Minnesota, and when when gardenlands is no reality nowhere Minnesota, then gardenlands is no reality somewhere Minnesota. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary duality, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary mis-duality, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary mis-duality, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary duality. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary mis-duality, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary dis-duality, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary dis-duality, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality binary mis-duality. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality photonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-photonics, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-photonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality photonics. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-photonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-photonics, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-photonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-photonics. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality phononics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-phononics, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-phononics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality phononics. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-phononics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-phononics, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-phononics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-phononics. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality hypnonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-hypnonics, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-hypnonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality hypnonics. And when the environment is the

environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary seconds, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary moments. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary seconds, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary minutes, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary minutes, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary seconds. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary minutes, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary hours, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary hours, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary minutes. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary hours, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary gaps, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary gaps, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary hours. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary gaps, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary cycles, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary cycles, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary gaps. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary cycles, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary days, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary days, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality looped momentary cycles. And when the environment is the no reality looped different day, then the environment is the no reality looped same day, and when the environment is the no reality looped same day, then the environment is the no reality looped different day. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality subsonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-subsonics, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-subsonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality subsonics. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-subsonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-subsonics, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-subsonics, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-subsonics. And when the environment is in the spectrum of the no reality future, then the environment is in the spectrum of the no reality past, and when the environment is in the spectrum of the no reality past, then the environment is in the spectrum of the no reality future. And when the environment is no reality 1st person, then the environment is no reality 3rd person, and when the environment is no reality 3rd person, then the environment is no reality 1st person. And when the environment is no reality 1st person, then the environment is no reality counter-1st person, and when the environment is no reality counter-1st person, then the environment is no reality 1st person. And when the environment is no reality 3rd person, then the environment is no reality counter-3rd person, and when the environment is no reality counter-3rd person, then the environment is no reality 3rd person. And when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality out of body experience, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality out of body counter-experience, and when the environment is the spectrum of a no reality out of body counter-experience, then the environment is the spectrum of a no reality out of body experience. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality blindness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality vision, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality vision, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality

blindness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality blindness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-blindness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-blindness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality blindness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality vision, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-vision, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter vision, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality vision. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality spectrums, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-spectrums, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-spectrums, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality spectrums. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality seeing things that aren't there, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-seeing things that aren't there, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-seeing things that aren't there, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality seeing things that aren't there. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedback, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedforward, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedforward, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedback. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedback, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedback, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedback, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedback. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedback, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-feedback, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-feedback, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedback. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedforward, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedforward, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedforward, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality feedforward. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedforward, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-feedforward, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-feedforward, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-feedforward. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality whimsicalness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-whimsicalness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-whimsicalness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality whimsicalness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-whimsicalness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-whimsicalness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality dis-whimsicalness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality mis-whimsicalness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality objects getting fractioned into fractioned objects, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-objects getting fractioned into fractioned counter-objects, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-objects getting fractioned into fractioned counter-objects, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality objects getting fractioned into fractioned objects. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality quantum weirdness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality quantum strangeness, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality quantum strangeness, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality quantum weirdness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality psychedelic inactivity, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality psychedelic activity, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality psychedelic activity, then the environment is

the spectrum of no reality psychedelic inactivity. And when the environment is the no reality conversion switch of a smoke, then the environment is the no reality conversion switch of a counter-smoke, and when the environment is the no reality conversion switch of a counter-smoke, then the environment is the no reality conversion switch of a smoke. And when the essence of the environment is no reality MDMA of itself, then the essence of the environment is no reality LSD of itself, and when the essence of the environment is no reality LSD of itself, then the essence of the environment is no reality MDMA of itself. And when the DreamScape environment is the essence of a no reality rabbithole walk, then the DreamScape environment is the essence of a no reality counter-rabbithole walk, and when the DreamScape environment is the essence of a no reality counter-rabbithole walk, then the DreamScape environment is the essence of a no reality rabbithole walk. And when something about the environment brain synthesises something into a no reality travelling-element, then nothing about the environment brain synthesises nothing into a no reality counter-travelling-element, and when nothing about the environment brain synthesises nothing into a no reality counter-travelling-element, then something about the environment brain synthesises something into a no reality travelling-element. And when something about the environment brain synthesises a no reality travelling-element into a travelling-molecule, then nothing about the environment brain synthesises a no reality counter-travelling-element into a counter-travelling-molecule, and when nothing about the environment brain synthesises a no reality counter-travelling-element into a counter-travelling-molecule, then something about the environment brain synthesises a no reality travelling-element into a travelling-molecule. And when something about the environment brain synthesises a no reality travelling molecule into a travelling-chemical, then nothing about the environment brain synthesises a no reality counter-travelling-molecule into a counter-travelling-chemical, and when nothing about the environment synthesises a no reality counter-travelling-molecule into a counter-travelling-chemical, then something about the environment brain synthesis a no reality travelling molecule into a travelling-chemical. And when somethinged something yet nothing about the environment brain synthesises a no reality travelling-chemical into a travelling-something-compound, then nothinged nothing yet something about the environment brain synthesises a no reality counter-travelling-chemical into a travelling-nothing-compound, and when nothinged nothing yet something about the environment brain synthesises a no reality counter-travelling-chemical into a travelling-nothing-compound, then somethinged something yet nothing about the environment brain synthesises a no reality travelling-chemical into a travelling-something-compound. And when something about the environment gives birth to a no reality somethinged model, then nothing about the environment gives life to a no reality nothinged model, and when nothing about the environment gives life to a no reality nothinged model, then something about the environment gives birth to a no reality somethinged model. And when the environment is no reality upside-down, then the environment is no reality counter-upside-down, and when the environment is no reality counter-upside-down, then the environment is no reality upside-down. And when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something synthwaved, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing counter-synthwaved, and when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing counter-synthwaved, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something synthwaved. And when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing synthwaved, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something

counter-synthwaved, and when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something counter-synthwaved, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing synthwaved. And when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something lusted, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing counter-lusted, and when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing counter-lusted, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something lusted. And when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing lusted, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something counter-lusted, and when the environment has the quantum effects of no reality something counter-lusted, then the environment has the quantum effects of no reality nothing lusted. And when the environment is no reality non-scriptedness, then the environment is no reality non-counter-scriptedness, and when the environment is no reality non-counter-scriptedness, then the environment is no reality non-scriptedness. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality unanswerability, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-unanswerability, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-unanswerability, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality unanswerability. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of nothing, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of something, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of something, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of nothing. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of nothinged nothing, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of somethinged something, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of somethinged something, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of nothinged nothing. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality panoramic, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-panoramic, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-panoramic, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality panoramic. And when the environment is no reality naturally supernatural, then the environment is no reality naturally counter-supernatural, and when the environment is no reality naturally counter-supernatural, then the environment is no reality naturally supernatural. And when nothing in the environment is the no reality spectrum of something, then counter-nothing in the environment is the no reality spectrum of something, and when counter-nothing in the environment is the no reality spectrum of something, then nothing in the environment is the no reality spectrum of something. And when the environment is no reality imaginary, then the environment is no reality counter-imaginary, and when the environment is no reality counter-imaginary, then the environment is no reality imaginary. And when the environment is the no reality ground state, then the environment is the no reality counter-ground state, and when the environment is the no reality counter-ground state, then the environment is the no reality ground state. And when the quantum environment is the no reality spectrum of size, then the quantum environment is the no reality spectrum of effects, and when the quantum environment is the no reality spectrum of effects, then the quantum environment is the no reality spectrum of size, because quantum is everything. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of the multi-verse, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of the counter-multi-verse, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of the counter-multi-verse, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of the multi-verse. And when the environment is the spectrum of no reality channels, then the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-channels, and when the environment is the spectrum of no reality counter-channels,

then the environment is the spectrum of no reality channels. And when the environment gets no reality saved, then the environment gets no reality counter-saved, and when the environment gets no reality counter-saved, then the environment gets no reality saved. And when the environment is no reality no appearance, then the environment is no reality no counter-appearance, and when the environment is no reality no counter-appearance, then the environment is no reality no appearance. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of clouds, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of counter-clouds, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of counter-clouds, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of clouds. And when something about the environment is the no reality spectrum of something, then something about the environment is the no reality spectrum of gnihtemos, and when something about the environment is the no reality spectrum of gnihtemos, then something about the environment is the no reality spectrum of something. And when nothing about the environment is the no reality spectrum of nothing, then nothing about the environment is the no reality spectrum of gnihton, and when nothing about the environment is the no reality spectrum of gnihton, then nothing about the environment is the no reality spectrum of nothing. And when something about the environment is the no reality PointBlankLoop, then nothing about the environment is the no reality PointBlankLoop, and when nothing about the environment is the no reality PointBlankLoop, then something about the environment is the no reality PointBlankLoop. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of objects, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of 2D+2ExtraD objects, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of 2D+2ExtraD objects, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of objects. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of satanic, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of counter-satanic, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of counter-satanic, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of satanic. And when the environment is no reality impossible, then the environment is no reality possible, and when the environment is no reality possible, then the environment is no reality impossible. And when the environment is no reality certain, then the environment is no reality uncertain, and when the environment is no reality uncertain, then the environment is no reality certain. And when the environment is no reality void, then the environment is the no reality dark void, and when the environment is the no reality dark void, then the environment is no reality void. And when the environment is no reality never, then the environment is no reality ever, and when the environment is no reality ever, then the environment is no reality never. And when something or nothing about the environment has no reality happened, then something or nothing about the environment will no reality happen, and when something or nothing about the environment will no reality happen, then something or nothing about the environment has no reality happened. And when the environment has a no reality date, then the environment has a no reality counter-date, and when the environment has a no reality counter-date, then the environment has a no reality date. And when once a day per year in the environment where no reality LSD gets activated, then once a day per counter-year in the environment where no reality LSD gets counter-activated, and when once a day per counter-year in the environment where no reality LSD gets counter-activated, then once a day per year in the environment where no reality LSD gets activated, where the reason why this happens is because LSD is a counter-fracture mechanism, that will happen and is happening once a day per year on a Sunday, therefore LSD Sunday is the day of the year that the environment gets counter-

fractured, which is a healthy thing for the environment and will maintain the environments health. [LSD, the counter-fracture mirror serum for the environment, pure psychedelic hallucinogenic atomic vapour](#), of the atoms nucleus being released. And when the environment is a no reality binary true 0, then the environment is a no reality binary false 1, and when the environment is a no reality binary false 1, then the environment is a no reality binary true 0. And when the environment is no reality either when when either, then the environment is no reality when either either when, and when the environment is no reality when either either when, then the environment is no reality either when when either. And when the environment is no reality where either either where, then the environment is no reality either where where either, and when the environment is no reality either where where either, then the environment is no reality where either either where. And when the environment is no reality date either either date, then the environment is no reality either date date either, and when the environment is no reality either date date either, then the environment is no reality date either either date. And when subsonic MDMA in the environment is no reality activated on a Friday once a month, then subsonic MDMA in the environment is no reality counter-activated on a counter-Friday once a month, and when subsonic MDMA in the environment is no reality counter-activated on a counter-Friday once a month, then subsonic MDMA in the environment is no reality activated on a Friday once a month. And when the day of Monday in the environment is no reality quantum weirdness day of orbs, then the day of counter-Monday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-orbs, and when the day of counter-Monday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of coiunter-orbs, then the day of Monday in the environment is no reality quantum weirdness day of orbs. And when the day of Tuesday in the environment is no reality quantum weirdness day of strings, then the day of counter-Tuesday in the environment is no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-strings, and when the day of counter-Tuesday in the environment is no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-strings, then the day of Tuesday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of strings. And when the day of Wednesday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of vibrations, then the day of counter-Wednesday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-vibrations, and when the day of counter-Wednesday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-vibrations, then the day of Wednesday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of vibrations. And when the day of Thursday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of waves, then the day of counter-Thursday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-waves, and when the day of counter-Thursday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-waves, then the day of Thursday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of waves. And when the day of Friday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of patterns, then the day of counter-Friday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-patterns, and when the day of counter-Friday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-patterns, then the day of Friday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of patterns. And when the day of Saturday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of fields, then the day of counter-Saturday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-fields, and when the day of counter-Saturday in the environment

is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-fields, then the day of Saturday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of fields. And when the day of Sunday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of fluctuations, then the day of counter-Sunday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-fluctuations, and when the day of counter-Sunday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness counter-day of counter-fluctuations, then the day of Sunday in the environment is the no reality quantum weirdness day of fluctuations. And when the environment is no reality enchanting, then the environment is no reality counter-enchanting, and when the environment is no reality counter-enchanting, then the environment is no reality enchanting. And when the environment is no reality no constant, the environment is no reality no counter-constant, and when the environment is no reality no counter-constant, then the environment is no reality no constant, where as well, the most perpetual thing is LSD, which lasts no longer than 12 hours, where something perpetual is the matter of looking, where as well, LSD is the 0th psychedelic, the only pure psychedelic. where as well, LSD is the 0th psychedelic, the only pure psychedelic. And when the environment has no reality thoughtful decisions, then the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-decisions, and when the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-decisions, then the environment has no reality thoughtful decisions. And when the environment has no reality thoughtful thinking, then the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-thinking, and when the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-thinking, then the environment has no reality thoughtful thinking. And when the environment has no reality thoughtful reasons, then the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-reasons, and when the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-reasons, then the environment has no reality thoughtful reasons. And when the environment has no reality thoughtful thoughts, then the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-thoughts, and when the environment has no reality thoughtful counter-thoughts, then the environment has no reality thoughtful thoughts. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of no belief, then someone in the environment will be no reality believable, and when someone in the environment will be no reality believable, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of no belief. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of one pure thing, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of one pure counter-thing, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of one pure counter-thing, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of one pure thing. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of one false object, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of one false counter-object, and when the environment is the spectrum of one false counter-object, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of one false object. And when the environment has the no reality spectrum of chaos magic, then the environment has the no reality one thing pure about magic that is chaos, and when the environment has the no reality one thing pure about magic that is chaos, then the environment has the no reality spectrum of chaos magic. And when the environment is the no reality spectrum of one thing master models, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of one thing counter-master models, and when the environment is the no reality spectrum of one thing counter-master models, then the environment is the no reality spectrum of one thing master models. And when the environment is no reality somethinged anything normal, then the environment is no reality somethinged anything computational, and when the environment is no reality somethinged anything computational, then the environment is no reality somethinged

anything normal. And when the environment is no reality nothinged anything counter-normal, then the environment is no reality nothinged anything counter-computational, and when the environment is no reality nothinged anything counter-computational, then the environment is no reality nothinged anything counter-normal. And when the environment is no reality everythinged something constant, then the environment is no reality everythinged something quantum, and when the environment is no reality everythinged something quantum, then the environment is no reality everythinged something constant. And when the environment is no reality everythinged nothing counter-constant, then the environment is no reality everythinged nothing counter-quantum, and when the environment is no reality everythinged nothing counter-quantum, then the environment is no reality everythinged nothing counter-constant. And if the no reality environment, then when the no reality environment, and when the no reality environment, then if the no reality environment. And when the no reality environment, then if the no reality environment, and if the no reality environment, then when the no reality environment. And if counter-if the no reality environment, then when counter-when the no reality environment, and when counter-when the no reality environment, then if counter-if the no reality environment. And when counter-when the no reality environment, then if counter-if the no reality environment, and if counter-if the no reality environment, then when counter-when the no reality environment. When somethinged everything about the environment is no reality something brained, then somethinged anything about the environment is no reality something brained, and when somethinged anything about the environment is no reality something brained, then somethinged everything about the environment is no reality something brained. And when nothinged everything about the environment is no reality nothing counter-brained, then nothinged anything about the environment is no reality nothing counter-brained, and when nothinged anything about the environment is no reality nothing counter-brained, then nothinged everything about the environment is no reality nothing counter-brained. And when the environment is no reality posed, then the environment is no reality pretend, and when the environment is no reality pretend, then the environment is no reality posed. And when the environment is no reality appear disappear, then the environment is no reality disappear appear, and when the environment is no reality disappear appear, then the environment is no reality appear disappear. And when the environment is no reality disappear appear, then the environment is no reality appear disappear, and when the environment is no reality appear disappear, then the environment is no reality disappear appear. And when the environment is a no reality giant contradictory paradoxical paradoxical contradiction, then the environment is a no reality giant paradoxical contradictory contradictory paradoxical, and when the environment is no reality giant paradoxical contradictory contradictory paradoxical, then the environment is no reality contradictory paradoxical paradoxical contradiction. And when the environment is a no reality giant paradoxical contradictory contradictory paradoxical, then the environment is a no reality giant contradictory paradoxical paradoxical contradictory, and when the environment is a no reality giant contradictory paradoxical paradoxical contradictory, then the environment is a no reality paradoxical contradictory contradictory paradoxical. And when the environment has no reality spectrum of looks, then the environment has no reality spectrum of feelings, and when the environment has no reality spectrum of feelings, then the environment has no reality spectrum of looks. And when the environment has no reality spectrum feelings, then the environment has no reality spectrum of looks, and when the environment has no reality

spectrum of looks, then the environment has no reality spectrum of feelings. And when the environment is a no reality spectrum of re-imagined things and de-imagined things, then the environment is a no reality spectrum of new things, and when the environment is a no reality spectrum of new things, then the environment is a no reality spectrum of re-imagined things and de-imagined thing. And when the environment is no reality positive triangulation, then the environment is no reality negative triangulation, and when the environment is no reality negative triangulation, then the environment is no reality positive triangulation. And when the environment is no reality never ending, then the environment is no reality ever ending, and when the environment is no reality ever ending, then the environment is no reality never ending. And when the environment is no reality scientific method nothing logical, then the environment is no reality scientific method something logical, and when the environment is no reality scientific method something logical, then the environment is no reality scientific method nothing logical. And when the environment is no reality inferior superior, then the environment is no reality superior inferior, and when the environment is no reality superior inferior, then the environment is no reality inferior superior. And when the reflection of the environment is no reality black and white hexed-tiles, then the counter-reflection of the environment is no reality black and white hexed-counter-tiles, and when the counter-reflection of the environment is no reality black and white hexed-counter-tiles, then the reflection of the environment is no reality black and white hexed-tiles. And when the environment is no reality fluctuation randomness of 10% percented 30%, then the environment is no reality fluctuation randomness of 10% percented 70%, and when the environment is no reality fluctuation randomness of 10% percented 70%, then the environment is no reality fluctuation randomness of 10% percented 30%. And when the environment is a no reality chess game of gossip, then the environment is a no reality chess game of counter-gossip, and when the environment is a no reality chess game of counter-gossip, then the environment is a no reality chess game of gossip. And when the grandmaster environment is a no reality chess game of the year of gossiped 2028, then the grandmaster environment is a no reality chess game of the year of gossiped counter-2028, and when the grandmaster environment is a no reality chess game of the year of gossiped counter-2028, then the grandmaster environment is a no reality chess game of the year of gossiped 2028. And when the environment is a no reality non-contradiction contradiction, then the environment is a no reality contradictory non-contradiction, and when the environment is a no reality contradictory non-contradiction, then the environment is a no reality non-contradiction contradiction. And when the dark void of the environment is the no reality anti-void, then the dark void of the environment is the no reality counter-anti-void, and when the dark void of the environment is the no reality counter-anti-void, then the dark void of the environment is the no reality anti-void. And when the weirdness of the environment no reality sets weirdness of the environment, then weirdness of the environment no reality sets counter-weirdness of the environment, and when weirdness of the environment no reality set counter-weirdness of the environment, then weirdness of the environment no reality sets weirdness of the environment. And when strangeness of the environment no reality counter-sets strangeness of the environment, then strangeness of the environment no reality counter-counter-sets strangeness of the environment, and when the strangeness of the environment no reality counter-counter-sets strangeness of the environment, then strangeness of the environment no reality counter-sets strangeness of the environment. And when changeness of the environment no reality changes changeness of the

environment, then changeness of the environment no reality changes counter-changeness of the environment, and when changeness of the environment no reality changes counter-changeness of the environment, then changeness of the environment no reality changes counter-changeness of the environment. And when the environment is a no reality idea, then the environment is a no reality cartoon of something, and when the environment is a no reality cartoon of something, then the environment is a no reality idea. And when the environment is a no reality virus, then the environment is a no reality counter-virus, and when the environment is a no reality counter-virus, then the environment is a no reality virus. And when the environment is the no reality lingering essence of something fantasy, then the environment is the no reality lingering essence of nothing fantasy, and when the environment is the no reality essence of nothing fantasy, then the environment is the no reality lingering essence of something fantasy. And when the environment is no reality squished, then the environment is no reality squeezed, and when the environment is no reality squeezed, then the environment is no reality squished. And when the environment is no reality inside a black hole that is something-not, then the environment is no reality inside a black hole that is nothing-not, and when the environment is no reality inside a black hole that is nothing-not, then the environment is no reality inside a black hole that is something-not, where the shell of a black hole is hell and heaven, the light void, inside a black hole is the dark void, nightmares, and the nucleus of a black void is the white void, dream-time! And when the environment is no reality nevertheless never, then the environment is no reality never never, and when the environment is no reality never never, then the environment is no reality nevertheless never. The day that I am forever set on and the day that I in the most constant way relive, is the day that I purely experienced LSD, by falling asleep on around two LSD tabs. And when the environment is strange, then the environment is something else, and when the environment is something else, then the environment is strange. And when the environment is weird, then the environment is something else, and when the environment is something else, then the environment is weird. And when the environment is dream-time, then the environment is something else, and when the environment is something else, then the environment is dream-time. And when the environment is specified, then the environment is something else, and when the environment is something else, then the environment is specified. And when I am inside the environment, then I am inside something else, and when I am inside something else, then I am inside the environment. And when the environment is inside the extra 4th wall, then the environment is outside the extra 4th wall, and when the environment is outside the extra 4th wall, then the environment is inside the extra 4th wall. And when the environment is inside the extra 4th wall of supernatural, then the environment is outside the extra 4th wall of supernatural, and when the environment is outside the extra 4th wall of supernatural, then the environment is inside the extra 4th wall of supernatural. And when the environment is forever a phase transition, then the environment is forever out of a phase transition, and when the environment is forever out of a phase transition, then the environment is forever a phase transition. And when the environment is something, then the environment is something else, and when the environment is something else, then the environment is something. And when the environment is nothing, then the environment is nothing else, and when the environment is nothing else, then the environment is nothing. And when the environment is completely strange matter, then the environment is completely weird matter, and when the environment is completely weird matter, then the environment is completely strange matter. And when

the environment is absolutely god matter, then the environment is absolutely devil matter, and when the environment is absolutely devil matter, then the environment is absolutely god matter. And when the environment appears, then the environment appear appears, and when the environment appear appears, then the environment appears. And when the environment is a something else psychedelic, then the environment is a something else hallucinogen, and when the environment is a something else hallucinogen, then the environment is a something else psychedelic. And when the environment is a nothing else psychedelic, then the environment is a nothing else hallucinogen, and when the environment is a nothing else hallucinogen, then the environment is a nothing else psychedelic. And when the environment is home for the pagan devil, then the environment is home for mother nature, and when the environment is home for mother nature, then the environment is home for the pagan devil. And when the environment is pure confusion, then the environment is purely hypnotising, and when the environment is purely hypnotising, then the environment is pure confusion. And when the environment is the only pure experience, then the environment is the only pure counter-experience, and when the environment is the only pure counter-experience, then the environment is the only pure experience. And when the environment appears out of nowhere, then the environment appear appears out of nowhere, and when the environment appear appears out of nowhere, then the environment appears out of nowhere. And when the environment is born out of love, then the environment is born out of hate, and when the environment is born out of hate, then the environment is born out of love. And when the environment is only one thing that is strange acid, then the environment is only one thing that is weird acid, and when the environment is only one thing that is weird acid, then the environment is only one thing that is strange acid. And when the environment is the answer of a dream psychedelic, then the environment is the question of a nightmare hallucinogen, and when the environment is the question of a nightmare hallucinogen, then the environment is the answer of a dream psychedelic. And when the environment is the answer of a nightmare psychedelic, then the environment is the question of a dream hallucinogen, and when the environment is the question of a dream hallucinogen, then the environment is the answer of a nightmare psychedelic. And when the environment is the answer of a dream hallucinogen, then the environment is the question of a nightmare psychedelic, and when the environment is the question of a nightmare psychedelic, then the environment is the answer of a dream hallucinogen. And when the environment is the answer of a nightmare hallucinogen, then the environment is the question of a dream psychedelic, and when the environment is the question of a dream psychedelic, then the environment is the answer of a nightmare hallucinogen. And when the environment is the experience of inside the head, then the environment is the experience of outside the head, and when the environment is the experience of outside the head, then the environment is the experience of inside the head. All the environment is, is the essence of a question and answer rabbithole! A psychedelic question and a psychedelic answer and a hallucinogenic question and a hallucinogenic answer! So the question of what is the environment? Leads to the answer that the environment is the LSD rabbithole, and which LSD rabbithole? The quantum strangeness rabiithole?!? And the only answer about the environment, that when the environment is good, then the environment is bad, and when the environment is bad, then the environment is good, where goodness is the only behaviour that is rather impossible, and where goodness requires paradoxical contradictory behaviour to achieve it. Am I good? I'm a little bit

good and a little bit bad, and it isn't the rules I follow, but rather social norms. The social norm of strange behaviour, and the rule of weird behaviour.

Environment set, set in. Where the fiction of this set model, happens.

Fiction set, set in.

Truth set, set in. A truthfully false environment device that is a false environment device that is the environment device truth.

The something deeply revealed set place.